

which the probability of a good response to added fertilizer is high, and above which the probability is low.

The critical level of a particular nutrient is determined as follows:

$$\text{Yield (\%)} = \frac{\text{Yield without nutrient}}{\text{Yield with applied nutrient}} \times 100.$$

The method consists of superimposing

two intersecting lines on the soil test percent yield scatter diagram – one line parallel to the y -axis and the other to the x -axis, drawn in a manner that places the maximum number of points in the lower left and upper right quadrants. The point where the line drawn parallel to the y -axis cuts the x -axis is termed the critical level.

This approach was used with data from the field trials to establish critical

levels for organic carbon, available phosphorus, and exchangeable potassium in Sierra Leone's two dominant rice ecologies: uplands (41 trials) and inland valley swamps (19 trials).

Tables 1 and 2 indicate that fields with less than 2.4% organic carbon, 10 ppm phosphorus, and 0.07 meq exchangeable potassium/100 g soil should respond positively to the corresponding plant nutrients. ■

Nitrogen management in coarse-textured lowland rice soils

M. A. Singlachar, rice agronomist, Y. S. Veeraraja Urs, junior agronomist, and A. M. Sudhakar, research assistant, University of Agricultural Sciences, Regional Research Station, V. C. Farm, Mandya 571 405, Karnataka, India

Field studies on nitrogen efficiency have been in progress at this center under the International Network for Soil Fertility

and Fertilizer Evaluation in Rice (INSFFER) Program for the last two seasons. Under the program various nitrogen sources and application methods to rice have been tested on a red sandy loam soil (Alfisol) of intermediate fertility.

Among the several treatments listed, subsoil application of urea gave the best performance at both low and high nitrogen levels (see table). Mudball or supergranule application resulted in

equivalent grain yields. The response to sulfur-coated urea (SCU) was equally encouraging.

Nitrogen efficiency was highest with mudball application. Supergranule and SCU application gave comparable N efficiency. ■

Effects of sources of nitrogen and methods of application on rice yields and nitrogen efficiency, Mandya, Karnataka, 1977 and 1978 kharif.

Source	Method	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)			
		1977 kharif		1978 kharif	
		Low N, 28 kg N/ha	High N, 56 kg N/ha	Low N, 27 kg N/ha	High N, 54 kg N/ha
Control	No nitrogen	2.42 (00)	—	3.50 (00)	—
Urea	Best split (50%, 25%, and 25% N, at planting, tillering, and PI stage)	2.78 (13)	3.21 (14)	4.72 (45)	4.60 (20)
Urea	Basal – band placement in every other row	2.88 (17)	2.84 (8)	—	—
Urea	Basal – mudball for every pair of rows, 10–12 cm soil depth	4.16 (62)	4.83 (43)	—	—
Urea	Basal – supergranules for every pair of rows, 10–12 cm soil depth	3.79 (49)	4.65 (40)	5.12 (60)	5.87 (44)
Urea	Basal – plow sole application	—	—	5.15 (61)	5.72 (41)
SCU	Basal – broadcasting and incorporation	3.74 (47)	4.25 (33)	4.36 (32)	5.44 (36)
SCU	Basal – plow sole application	—	—	4.87 (51)	5.94 (45)
SCU	Basal – broadcasting and incorporation	—	—	4.45 (35)	5.39 (35)

^aFigures in parentheses indicate the nitrogen efficiency in kilogram grain/kilogram of applied N. Kharif = wet season. PI = panicle initiation.

	IR20	Rasi
General mean yield (t/ha)	3.55	5.03
CD at 0.05	0.63	0.64
CV (%)	12.70	10.00

Effect of azolla inoculation on rice yields

K. Govindarajan, S. Kannaiyan, R. Jagannathan, V. G. Palaniyandi, and M. Ramachandran, Paddy Experiment Stations, Tirur 602025 and Ambasamudram 627401, Tamil Nadu, India

The water fern azolla, in association with the blue-green algae *Anabaena azollae*, can fix atmospheric nitrogen and supply it to the rice crop after decomposition. The effects of azolla incorporation on rice yield were studied. A field experiment using IR20 was conducted in a randomized block design with four replications in the 1978–79navarai season. Treatments were:

- 0-50-50 kg NPK/ha
- 25-50-50 kg NPK/ha
- 50-50-50 kg NPK/ha
- 75-50-50 kg NPK/ha
- 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha
- 0-50-50 kg NPK/ha + azolla
- 25-50-50 kg NPK/ha + azolla
- 50-50-50 kg NPK/ha + azolla
- 75-50-50 kg NPK/ha + azolla
- 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha + azolla

Urea, superphosphate and muriate of potash were used as sources of N, P, and K. Seven days after transplanting, 300 g azolla/m² was inoculated. In about 2 weeks azolla covered the plot surface and was incorporated.

Azolla incorporation increased yields

significantly. Plots treated with 75-50-50 kg NPK + azolla yielded as well as those with 100-50-50 kg NPK alone (5.2 vs 5.4 t/ha), indicating that azolla might supplement 25 kg N/ha. The yield from 0-50-50 kg NPK + azolla (4.4 t/ha) was similar to that from

25-50-50 kg NPK/ha (4.6 t/ha).

A similar investigation was undertaken at the Ambasamudram Paddy Experiment Station in the 1978-79 kar season with the rice variety ADT31. The results show that the incorporation of azolla along with 50 kg N/ha gave yields equal

to those with 75 kg N/ha alone (5.9 t/ha) indicating a saving of 25 kg N/ha. Azolla incorporation with 100 kg N/ha was superior to 100 kg N/ha alone (6.5 vs 6.3 t/ha). The results clearly indicated the positive effect of azolla inoculation in increasing grain yield. ■

Field conditions suitable for blue-green algae multiplication

S. Srinivasan, assistant plant pathologist, Paddy Experiment Station, Aduthurai 612101, Tamil Nadu, India

To determine the optimal field conditions for growth of blue-green algae, a trial was conducted in March 1979 in a field rich in the algae. Six conditions (see table) were tried with four replications. In the 10-m² bundled plots of the experiment, water height was maintained at 5 cm. Superphosphate was applied to the plots at 160 kg P₂O₅/ha. To control pests on the algae, 250 g carbofuran 3% G was applied to each plot. Seedlings of ADT31 were used for the planted field treatment.

Blue-green algae^a yields. Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	Yield (kg/10 m ²)	Blue-green algae types in descending order of abundance
With fresh stubbles	5.84	M1, Ad, Pb
With stubbles up to soil surface	5.68	M1, Ad, Pb
Stubbles removed	3.96	M1, Ad, Pb
Stubbles incorporated	4.43	M1, Ad
Plowed, prepared without stubbles	3.16	M1, Ad
Planted field	6.23	M1, Ad
CD	0.36	

^a M1 = *Microcoleus lacustris*, Ad = *Anabaena doliolum*, Pb = *Plectonema boryanum*.

Twenty days after the treatments began, blue-green algae floating on the water surface were collected, dried, and weighed.

Blue-green algae multiplication was highest in the planted field (see table).

In the first three treatments, three types of blue-green algae – *Microcoleus lacustris*, *Anabaena doliolum*, and *Plectonema boryanum* – were observed. In the others, *P. boryanum* was not found. ■

Environment and its influence

Effect of air temperature on rice flower temperature

I. Nishiyama, visiting scientist from the Tropical Agriculture Research Center, Japan (currently assigned to the Plant Physiology Department, International Rice Research Institute)

The temperature inside rice flowers was measured at different air temperatures on days of fine weather under flooding in phytotron glasshouse rooms, growth cabinets, screenhouses, and fields at IRRI and at the Regional Rice Research Station, Punjab Agricultural University, Kapurthala, Punjab, India.

When ambient air temperature was lower than 30°C, the temperature inside the flower was slightly higher (see figure). When it was higher than 30°C, the temperature inside the flower was lower. The difference increased with rising

Difference between temp inside and near flower (°C)

Effect of air temperature on flower temperature in the rice plant.